

TEACHING ENGLISH TO ADULTS THROUGH VIDEO MATERIALS

¹Pardayeva Aziza, ²Kudratova Lola

¹English teacher at Samarkand State Institute of foreign languages, ²Sophomore student at
Samarkand State Institute of foreign languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10816700>

Abstract This article talks about how to develop and learn English and foreign languages for adults through video tutorials, video material, YouTube lessons, and how to improve the quality of learning English by using easier, interesting and effective methods.

Keywords: English environment, Online video lessons, YouTube, interactive methods, foreign languages, modern technologies, online platforms, marked memorization, distance education.

Introduction

The current globalization process requires people to learn other world languages, that is, foreign languages, in addition to their mother tongue. That is why, according to the researchers conducted by the leaders of scientific work, it is required to learn and know foreign languages not only for young people, but also for adults. Learning languages with older learners is easier than with younger children, and older people have the opportunity to work on themselves. That's why this article is about showing older adults easier ways to learn foreign languages. Learning any foreign language requires a lot of effort, but for older people, if they acquire knowledge, that is, understanding, then independent education, that is, increasing knowledge by working on themselves, does not require much effort.

In today's advanced age, acquiring knowledge from the other side of the world by phone does not cause any problems. Therefore, older language learners can easily learn foreign languages by themselves through video tutorials. That is, through the rational use of modern technologies, there is an opportunity to use time effectively without spending too much money.

English environment. If you are learning a foreign language, you must understand its environment and feel yourself in that environment, that is, in order to improve the quality of language acquisition. You name the world around you in English, and we can get a good result by making it a habit to make sentences and repeat them using them grammatically.

Modern Technology. Using modern technology, English can be made more interesting and memorable. For this, people need a personal computer, smartphone, tablet and other similar gadgets. Learning English using modern technologies means using online platforms, programs and textbooks.

There are many websites and platforms that teach English on the Internet. These include BBC Learning English, Duolingo, Babbel, British Council, Cambly, Coursera, FluentU, Lingoda, Alison, Italki, Preply, ABCya, edX, ELLLO, Future Learn, Grammarly, Verbing, Busuu, Cambridge English, English Central, Udemy, Memorise, Canva, platforms such as Perfectly Spoken are examples.

Features that make these platforms convenient are:

- the learner can learn at any time;
- appropriate programs are determined depending on the level of knowledge of each student;
- online videos and images can illuminate relevant topics more widely, thereby broadening students' imagination and making it easier to remember;

- upon completion of a certain program, a certificate or a document confirming the completion of the course is awarded;

- all lessons are in electronic format, so you can download them anytime and on different gadgets.

YouTube. YouTube is one of the modern technologies, and this program is very important in improving English grammar and other skills by listening to various useful channels and attending lessons from experienced teachers. Readers can use it to watch English channels or watch their favorite foreign shows and news with video subtitles. Although all these captions should be informative i.e. if they are teaching you the right thing, try to use them after knowing if the channel is reliable or not. There are many benefits to enjoying these shows as long as you feel comfortable listening to them at your hearing level.

Character memorization. We know that knowing new words plays an important role in learning a foreign language, so it is necessary to pay special attention to vocabulary when learning a language.

The best way to do this is to stick the words you memorized today on a sticker in a prominent place, and by repeating it every time you see it, it will be easier and better to remember. For example, you can write or hang new words and phrases on stickers in places where you spend a lot of time and reinforce the words by repeating them while using the item or every time you visit the place. It can be added that translating terms from the local language to English is also useful for you, by creating a foreign language environment for yourself, you can master the language in a short time.

Summary

In conclusion, adult language learners do not consider learning English as an obligation, but using free time effectively, but interesting video lessons, feeling in the environment of that language, innovative methods, using modern technologies will help them develop their future work activities.

REFERENCES

1. Pardayeva Aziza, & Normurodov Afr o‘zbek. (2023). MODERN METHODS OF ORGANIZING FOREIGN LANGUAGES LESSONS. European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 21, 170–172.
2. <https://preply.com/en/blog/websites-to-learn-english/>
3. English language teaching documents general editor: C.J.Brumft" Video Applications in English Language age teaching
4. Kudratova Lola, Zubaydova Nilufar" BOLALARGA INGLIZ TILINI NOODATIY INTERFAOL USULLAR ORQALI O‘RGATISH"